

**MAIN FEATURES OF ACTIVITIES BASED ON IMPROVING COMMUNICATIVE
COMPETENCES OF 5-6 GRADERS**

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Abstract. *This article highlights main features of activities on the basis of improving 5-6 graders' communicative competences such lexis, pragmatic, discourse and strategic in English classroom.*

Keywords: *features, communicative competence activities, communicative competence*

The formation of a person's communicative competence occurs in various areas of activity throughout life. In accordance with the needs of the time, it is necessary not only to provide schoolchildren with theoretical knowledge, but also to develop skills that are in demand in future professional and everyday communication. Mastering the stylistic capabilities of the foreign language, all its diversity, and 5-6 graders should be able to model their own statements in various communication situations, understanding that speech is a person's "calling card", indicating their intellectual level and personal qualities.

Senior school age has been studied from the point of view of speech and communication development much less than other age groups, although it is the most important stage in the mental maturation of the individual, as well as a period of qualitative changes in the formation of speech-thinking and communicative activity.

Modern psychological research suggests that one of the important characteristics of a person studying in high school is the growth of self-awareness, which determines the level of demands both on oneself and on others. [Bojovich, 1995; Tolstix, 2003 and etc]

Fifth- and sixth-grade students are in a period of rapid cognitive and social development. They are becoming more independent and assertive, and they are eager to express their own ideas and opinions. This is reflected in their oral and communicative activity, which is characterized by the following features:

Increased complexity and sophistication: Fifth- and sixth-grade students are able to engage in more complex and sophisticated oral communication than younger students. They can use more complex vocabulary and grammar structures, and they can discuss more abstract and challenging topics.

Greater focus on critical thinking and problem-solving: Fifth- and sixth-grade students are able to think more critically about what they are saying and hearing. They can analyze information, identify arguments, and draw conclusions. They can also use their oral communication skills to solve problems and make decisions.

Greater interest in social and global issues: Fifth- and sixth-grade students are increasingly interested in social and global issues. They want to learn about different cultures and perspectives, and they want to use their oral communication skills to make a difference in the world.

Activities based on developing communicative competence in the English classroom of 5–6 graders should be characterized by the following features:

- **Authenticity:** The activities should be relevant to students' lives and experiences. They should also reflect real-world communication situations. For example, students could role-

play a conversation with a customer service representative or order food at a restaurant in English. [3]

- **Interactivity:** The activities should allow students to interact with each other and with the teacher. This could involve pair work, group work, or whole-class discussions. [4]

- **Collaboration:** The activities should provide opportunities for students to work together and learn from each other. This could involve group projects, presentations, or debates. [5]

- **Feedback:** The activities should provide students with feedback on their performance. This feedback should be timely and specific, and it should help students identify their strengths and weaknesses. [6]

- **Differentiation:** The activities should be adapted to meet the needs of all learners. This could involve providing students with different levels of difficulty for the same task or allowing them to choose activities that match their interests. [7]

Here are some examples of communicative competence activities that can be used in the English classroom for 5–6 graders:

Role-playing: Students can role-play a variety of different conversations, such as ordering food at a restaurant, asking for directions, or giving a presentation.

Debates: Students can debate current events, topics, or controversial issues.

Group presentations: Students can work together to create and deliver a presentation on a topic they have been studying in class.

Storytelling: Students can write and tell their own stories, or they can retell traditional stories from different cultures.

Video conferencing: Students can video conference with other students and teachers from all over the world to practice their English skills.

Corpus: students can boost their range of vocabulary and grammar by using authentic materials

When planning communicative competence activities for 5–6 graders, it is important to keep the following tips in mind:

- **Making sure the activities are age-appropriate.** The activities should be challenging enough to engage students, but they should not be so difficult that students become frustrated.

- **Providing students with clear instructions and expectations.** Students need to know what they are supposed to do and what is expected of them in order to be successful.

- **Giving students time to prepare.** Students need time to think about what they are going to say and to practice their speaking skills before they participate in an activity.

- **Circulating around the room and provide support.** As students are participating in activities, circulate around the room and provide support as needed. This could involve answering questions, offering feedback, or providing encouragement.

- **Celebrating students' successes.** It is important to celebrate students' successes, no matter how small they may seem. This will help students feel confident in their abilities and motivated to continue learning.

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